

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Fourteen

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm Fourteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁰ For the choir director. <i>A Psalm</i> of David.</p> <p>Psa. 14:1 The fool has said in his heart, "There is no God." They are corrupt, they have committed abominable deeds; There is no one who does good.</p> <p>² The LORD has looked down from heaven upon the sons of men To see if there are any who understand, Who seek after God.</p> <p>³ They have all turned aside, together they have become corrupt; There is no one who does good, not even one.</p> <p>Psa. 14:4 Do all the workers of wickedness not know, Who eat up my people <i>as</i> they eat bread, <i>And</i> do not call upon the LORD? ⁵ There they are in great dread, For God is with the righteous generation.</p> <p>⁶ You would put to shame the counsel of the afflicted, But the LORD is his refuge.</p> <p>Psa. 14:7 Oh, that the salvation of Israel would come out of Zion! When the LORD restores His captive people, Jacob will rejoice, Israel will be glad.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 14:1</p> <p style="text-align: right;">נָבַל בְּלִבּוֹ אֵין אֱלֹהִים הַשְׁחִיתוּ הַתְּעִיבוּ עַל־יְלֵה אֵין עֲשֵׂה- טוֹב : ² יְהוָה מִשָּׁמַיִם הַשְׁקִיף עַל-בְּנֵי-אָדָם לְרֹאוֹת הַיָּשׁ מִשְׁכִּיל דָרַשׁ אֶת-אֱלֹהִים : ³ הַכֹּל סָר יַחְדָּו נֶאֱלְחוּ אֵין עֲשֵׂה-טוֹב אֵין גַּם-אֶחָד : ⁴ הֲלֹא יָדְעוּ כָל-פֶּעַלִי אֲנִי אֹכְלִי עַמִּי אֲכָלוּ לֶחֶם יְהוָה לֹא קָרְאוּ : ⁵ שָׁם אִפְתָּרוּ פֶתַח כִּי- אֱלֹהִים בְּרוּר צַדִּיק : ⁶ עֵצַת- עֲנִי תִבְיֹשׁ כִּי יִתְּנָה מַחְסֵהוּ : ⁷ מִי יִתֵּן מִצִּיּוֹן יְשׁוּעַת יִשְׂרָאֵל בְּשׁוּב יְהוָה שְׁבוֹת עַמּוֹ יִגַּל יַעֲקֹב יִשְׂמַח יִשְׂרָאֵל :</p>

Targum

Psa. 14:1 For praise; in the spirit of prophecy through David. The fool said in his heart, "There is no rule of God on the earth." They corrupted their deeds, they despised goodness and found iniquity. There is none who does good. ²The LORD looked down from heaven on the sons of men to see if there was any wise man seeking instruction from the presence of the LORD. ³All alike have turned backward, they have become lax; there is none who does good, there is not even one. ⁴Do they not know, all doers of falsehood? Those among my people who dine have dined on bread [and] not blessed the name of the LORD. ⁵There they became afraid because the word of the LORD is in the generation of the righteous. ⁶You will despise the counsel of the poor man, because he has placed his hope in the LORD. ⁷Who will produce from Zion the redemption of Israel? When the LORD brings back the exile of his people, Jacob will rejoice, Israel will be glad.

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>The fool has said in his heart, "There is no God." They are corrupt, they have committed abominable deeds; There is no one who does good.</p>	<p>לְמַנְצֵחַ לַדָּוָד אָמַר נָבֵל בְּלִבּוֹ אֵין אֱלֹהִים הַשְׁחִיתוּ הַתְּעִיבוּ עַל־יָדָהּ אֵין עֲשֵׂה-טוֹב :</p>

Verse Analysis

Psalm 13 voiced a faith that has sustained Israel since its inception. This faith has kept the Hebrew people together throughout its long period of destitution.

נָבֵל (naval) verb, be senseless, foolish. It can also be translated as "withered." History has shown that whenever humans become foolish, they enter into a time of mental and moral degradation.

Israel's enemies called them foolish for their faith and hope in the LORD. As long as Israel kept their covenant with the LORD, they were always protected. נָבֵל denotes the disappearance of unfettered moral strength. The nation was "going down the tubes," and it appeared that no one could stop it.

הַשְּׂחֵחַתוֹ הֶתְעֵיבוּ עֲלֵיהֶם (hesheecheeto heteeeevoo alala) – denotes that when human actions are left unchecked, they become abominations.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To Netzach, a Sefirot of the Tree of Life by David. In his heart, the foolish man has said, "There is no God"; they are corrupt and an abomination because their activities are not those of a person who wants to do good.

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>² The LORD has looked down from heaven upon the sons of men To see if there are any who understand, Who seek after God.</p>	<p>יְהוָה מִשָּׁמַיִם הִשְׁקִיף עַל-בְּנֵי- אָדָם לִרְאוֹת תֵּינֵשׁ</p>

Verse Analysis

Humans who deny the existence of the LORD do so because the LORD cannot be detected by reason.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD observes from Heaven to find humans who are searching for Him by using their reason.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>³ They have all turned aside, together they have become corrupt; There is no one who does good, not even one.</p>	<p>הַכֹּל סָר־יָחַדוּ נְאֻלְתּוּ אֵין עֲשֵׂה-טוֹב אֵין גַּם-אֶחָד :</p>

Verse Analysis

At the time of this writing, the author believed that every person was corrupt and had turned away from the LORD. Therefore, the LORD does not need to intervene and bring punishment to the people because every member of society serves as a punishment for his/her fellow citizens. In other words, the people punish each other by their violence toward each other.

There have often been periods when all humanity seemed to be corrupted, and no one does anything good.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

All humanity is depraved. No one is doing anything good, not a single person.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
Do all the workers of wickedness not know, Who eat up my people <i>as</i> they eat bread, <i>And</i> do not call upon the LORD?	הֲלֹא יָדְעוּ כָּל-פְּעֻלֵי אֹנֶן אֲכָלֵי עַמִּי אֲכָלוּ לֶחֶם יִהְיֶה לֵא קִרְאוּ :

Verse Analysis

Even when it appears that all humanity is corrupt and perverted, there has always been a nation that respected the LORD and obeyed His divine law. That nation is Israel. Without Israel, the world would have become completely lost.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The doers of violence do not know who devours Israel like a person eating bread and has not invited the LORD?

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
There they are in great dread, For God is with the righteous generation	נֶשֶׁם אֶפְתָּחוּ פֶתַח כִּי-אֱלֹהִים בְּדֹר צְדִיק

Verse Analysis

פֶתַח פֶתַח (gachadoo gachad) – this phrase is the verb and noun of the same word. Therefore, it means "great dread." The great dread was coming upon the people who chose not to know the LORD and preyed upon His nation Israel. These people were enslaved to their lustful desires and thus forfeited all moral freedom.

צְדִיק (*saddîq*) just, lawful, righteous. The root word connotes conformity to an ethical or moral standard. צְדִיק, then, refers to an ethical, moral standard and of course in the Old Testament, that standard is the nature and will of God. "The Lord is righteous (צְדִיק) in all his ways and holy in all his works" (Ps 145:17).

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

They learned to fear the LORD because they found the LORD in the history of the righteous (Israel).

Verse Six and Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁶ You would put to shame the counsel of the afflicted, But the LORD is his refuge.</p> <p>⁷ Oh, that the salvation of Israel would come out of Zion! When the LORD restores His captive people, Jacob will rejoice, Israel will be glad.</p>	<p>⁶ עֵצַת-עֲנִי תִבְיָשׁוּ כִּי יְהוָה מִתְּסֵהוּ : ⁷ מִי יִתֵּן מִצִּיּוֹן יְשׁוּעַת יִשְׂרָאֵל בְּשׁוּב יְהוָה שְׁבוֹת עַמּוֹ יִגַּל יַעֲקֹב יִשְׂמַח יִשְׂרָאֵל :</p>

Verse Analysis

These two verses conclude the Psalm. The Jewish people have, throughout their tribulations, placed all their trust in the LORD.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

You mock the counsel of the afflicted who trusts in the LORD. Who is it that extends Israel's help from Zion? One day the LORD will restore his captive people and return them from exile. Jacob will rejoice, and Israel will attain joy.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To Netzach, a Sefirot of the Tree of Life by David. In his heart, the foolish man has said, "There is no God"; they are corrupt and an abomination because their activities are not those of a person who wants to do good.

The LORD observes from Heaven to find humans who are searching for Him by using their reason.

All humanity is depraved. No one is doing anything good, not a single person.

The doers of violence do not know who devours Israel like a person eating bread and has not invited the LORD?

They learned to fear the LORD because they found the LORD in the history of the righteous (Israel).

You mock the counsel of the afflicted who trusts in the LORD. Who is it that extends Israel's help from Zion? One day the LORD will restore his captive people and return them from exile. Jacob will rejoice, and Israel will attain joy.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

